

DIFFERENT TEACHING STRATEGIES USED FOR SPEAKING SKILL FOR A2 LEVEL LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses various teaching strategies for speaking skill which are commonly used in teaching and learning classrooms. These strategies are frequently utilized for A2 level learners. These teaching strategies are considered as common and effective strategies to improve speaking skill of A2 level learners. In this article the importance and effectiveness of some teaching strategies are mentioned.

Speaking is a skill for communicating and exchanging knowledge, as well as building long-term relationships. Speaking is a vital skill for language learning, yet it is difficult to learn and teach. Speaking is a major problem in language programs, and effective teaching practices play a significant role in achieving successful outcomes. Strategies for achieving speaking skills differ due to their distinct purpose. Speaking focuses on oral language. Speaking is a key component of language abilities, enabling efficient communication. To effectively convey their ideas, speakers must be confident and passionate. The most important aspect for students is their ability to communicate vocally with their classmates. Often, individuals struggle to express their beliefs, feelings, and ideas clearly and understandably. Many linguistics and ESL teachers now believe that students learn to speak in a second language through "interacting". Communicative language teaching and collaborative learning are most effective for achieving this goal. Communicative Language Teaching is based on real-life scenarios that demand communication. Using this strategy in ESL lessons allows students to communicate in their target language. To improve oral language, ESL teachers should develop a classroom environment that includes authentic activities and relevant objectives. This can happen when students work in groups to accomplish a goal or assignment.

Reiser and Dick suggest that teachers might utilize several instructional tactics to meet their learning objectives[1;23-28]. Cole asserts that it is the teacher's responsibility to create effective plans and procedures to meet students' educational requirements, with the goal of facilitating communication in the language being learned. Teachers are responsible for encouraging students to speak English through effective teaching tactics [2;107-112]. There are several speaking teaching strategies used in classrooms for different situations. Teaching tactics for speaking include cooperative exercises, role-play, creative projects, and drilling. One of the speaking strategies frequently used in classrooms is a role play. Role plays involve pupils

acting out various social situations and roles [3;66]. Role-playing enhances oral expression and growth empathy among students. Role-playing is crucial for developing speaking abilities since it improves interpersonal interactions, group work, and language proficiency. Therefore, the activities given should be vibrant and interactive. According to Jabbarova, attending a discussion group is a more casual and comfortable approach. This approach to English learning prioritizes conversation and relationship-building over speaking "correct" English[4;2]. Speaking English in this situation might improve your confidence in front of others. Creative tasks resemble real-life tasks as Solcova asserts that students develop their fluency best, if engaged in tasks where all their concentration focuses on producing something, rather than on the language itself [5;16]. In this case I agree that role plays are one of the best teaching activities that can help learners build fluency and self –confidence. According to Thornbury, drilling is a technique for improving pronunciation that involves copying and repeating words, phrases, and even entire sentences[6;58]. It helps pupils focus on new material by emphasizing key words and phrases. Using utterances can help students transfer new information from working memory to long-term memory and improve articulatory control. Another teaching strategies commonly used for speaking skill is games. Gamification can help language teachers engage and drive pupils to improve their speaking skills. The gamified environment improved students' comfort and confidence in using English, leading to increased passion for language acquisition. Including games for speaking skill for A2 level students promotes active involvement, skill improvement, and knowledge retention, which might be challenging for teachers to implement. According to Hammer , incorporating gamification in the classroom does not require changing the existing curriculum [7;82] . The goal is to combine relevant aspects of video games without focusing on a specific game. As a result, students' interest level increases. This evidence shows that the game's entertaining features are included, adapted, and used in the educational process. One other way of teaching speaking is story-telling. Students can summarize previously heard stories or write their own to share with their classmates. Storytelling stimulates creative thinking. It also helps pupils communicate their views in the type of story's inception, development, and end, as well as its characters and environment, are essential. Students can also tell riddles and jokes. For example, the teacher may start each class session by asking a few students to share brief riddles or jokes. This approach not only improves pupils' speaking skills, but also engages the entire class. In addition to this approach, there is a teaching strategy which is called “ picture narrating” which can be suitable for A2 level learners. This activity is based on a sequence of photos. Learners use a rubric provided by the teacher to narrate the tale portrayed in sequential photos. Rubrics might incorporate terminology and structures. They must use when narrating. Another way of teaching speaking using pictures is picture describing. To use photographs in speaking activities, provide a single picture and ask learners to describe its contents. For this activity, learners create groups and each receives a unique picture. Students discussed the picture . Groups create a picture, and each group's spokesman presents it to the entire class. This practice helps learners develop creativity, imagination, and public speaking skills. Another teaching strategy which can be suitable for A2 level learners is finding difference. In this activity, students work in pairs and receive two different photographs, such as boys playing football and girls playing tennis. Students in pairs discuss the similarities and/or differences in the images.

Summary. To sum up, for teaching English speaking skill for A2 level learners several teaching strategies have been used including role plays , games, discussions. These teaching strategies are considered as common and beneficial teaching strategies and gives an opportunity for learners to be able to speak and communicate in English. Teaching speaking is a critical component of second language learning. Clear and efficient communication in a second language improves academic performance and overall achievement in life. Thus, it is critical that language teachers devote significant emphasis to teaching speaking. To encourage meaningful conversation among students, a rich learning environment is preferred over memorization. Speaking activities like the ones listed above can help pupils build essential communication skills for life. These activities increase student engagement and make learning more relevant and enjoyable.

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